

Can Messinian brines impact the evolution of a Fe-Skarn? The case of Serifos (Cyclades, Hellas)

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Fluid inclusions in the synkinematic Serifos Fe-skarn system (Cyclades, Hellas) track the evolution of the hydrothermal system and the provenance of the involved fluids. Proximal quartz exhibits complex cathodoluminescence patterns with oscillatory zoning and overgrowths, and hosts boiling assemblages of coexisting Na-Ca-K-Fe-Cl brine and vapour inclusions. Salinities reach up to 40% NaCl_{eq} and homogenisation temperatures range from 370 to 170 °C. Baryte and iron oxide precipitate in quartz's outer growth zones and coexist with brines of reduced salinity (~22% NaCl_{eq}) and low-salinity fluid inclusions, enriched in vapour-partitioning elements (Li, B, S, As, Sb, I). We interpret the latter as contracted vapours. Depressurisation, cooling, mixing with oxidised external fluids and ore deposition are observed down to the growth zone level (Fig. 1).

Despite dilution, proximal mineralisation retains a magmatic signature, as evidenced by LA-ICP-MS fluid inclusion analysis. Halogen ratios (Cl-Br-I) reveal a transition from magmatic to residual brine signatures from the proximal to the detachment-bound distal parts of the system. Uniform fluid δD of -14 to -30‰, yet strongly variable $\delta^{18}O$ values between proximal and distal mineralisation suggest progressive fluid mixing.

Considering the intrusion's Upper Miocene age, hydrothermal activity persisted during the Messinian Salinity Crisis. Our data demonstrate that Messinian evaporitic brines infiltrated the system via the West Cycladic Detachment System and played a substantial role in its evolution.

- Primary FIAs
- Pseudosecondary FIAs
- Salinity (% NaCleq)
- Th (°C)

